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COMPUTER NETWORKS RESEARCH PAPER

[21CS52]

CLOUD COMPUTING NETWORKING

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2023-24

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing materializes the vision of utility computing. Tenants can benefit from on-demand provisioning of compute, storage and networking resources according to a pay-peruse business model. Tenants have only limited visibility and control over network resources. The owners of cloud computing facilities are also facing challenges in various aspect of providing and efficiently managing infrastructure as a service (IaaS) facility. In this work we present the networking issues in IaaS and federation challenges that are currently addressed with existing technologies. We also present innovative software-define networking (SDN) proposals, which are applied to some of the challenges and could be used in future deployments as efficient

Virtual networking and extensions of cloud computing facilities along with federation issues are the focus of this work. SDN as a novel and innovative mechanism provides proper solutions for these issues, which are also included in a comparison of virtual networking techniques. A high-level SDN-based cloud federation framework as an innovative opportunity is presented in this work and the last part of this paper concludes our contribution.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, cloud computing has rapidly emerged as a widely accepted computing paradigm built around core concepts such as on-demand computing resources, elastic scaling, elimination of up-front investment, reduction of operational expenses, and establishing a pay-per-usage business model for information technology and computing services. There are different models of cloud computing that are offered today as services like Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). IaaS, which is the focus of this work, refers to the capability that is provided to the consumers to provision processing, storage and networks, and other fundamental computing resources where they are able to deploy and run arbitrary software. The consumer does not manage or control the underlying cloud infrastructure but has control over operating systems, storage, deployed applications, and possibly selected networking components (e.g., firewalls, load balancers, etc.). Amazon is arguably the first major proponent of IaaS through its Elastic Computing Cloud (EC2) service.

Cloud-computing technology is still evolving. Various companies, standards bodies, and alliances are addressing several remaining gaps and concerns. Some of these concerns are: What are the challenges behind the virtual networking in IaaS deployment? What are the potential solutions using the existing technologies for the implementation of virtual networks inside IaaS vision? Is there any room to utilize innovative paradigms like Software Defined Networking (SDN) to address virtual networking challenges? When cloud federation (or even cloud bursting) is involved, should the servers in the cloud be on the same Layer 2 network as the servers in the enterprise or, should a Layer 3 topology be involved because the cloud servers are on a network outside the enterprise? In addition, how would this approach work across multiple cloud data centers?

Consider a case where an enterprise uses two separate cloud service providers. Compute and storage resource sharing along with common authentication (or migration of authentication information) are some of the problems with having the clouds “interoperate.” For virtualized cloud services, VM migration is another factor to be considered in federation. In this work we present a tutorial of networking in IaaS and key challenges and issues, which should be addressed using existing technologies or novel and innovative mechanisms.

NETWORKING IN IAAS:

Although cloud computing does not necessarily depend on virtualization, several cloud infrastructures are built with virtualized servers. Within a virtualized environment, some of the networking functionalities (e.g., switching, firewall, application-delivery controllers, and load balancers) can reside inside a physical server. Consider the case of the software-based Virtual Switch as shown in Figure 1. The Virtual switch inside the same physical server can be used to switch the traffic between the VMs and aggregate the traffic for connection to the external physical switch. The Virtual Switch is often implemented as a plug-in to the hypervisor. The VMs have virtual Ethernet adapters that connect to the Virtual Switch, which in turn connects to the physical Ethernet adapter on the server and to the external Ethernet switch. Unlike physical switches, the Virtual Switch does not necessarily have to run network protocols for its operation, nor does it need to treat all its ports the same because it knows that some of them are connected to virtual Ethernet ports. It can function through appropriate configuration from an external management entity.

Fig 1: A typical data-center switched network architecture:

Network architecture is one of the key building blocks of cloud computing. A cloud user connects to the network to access the cloud resources. The cloud is accessible through a public network (the Internet) or through a private network infrastructure (e.g., MPLS or dedicated links). The most significant effect of cloud computing on network is in the data center. The data center consists mainly of servers in the racks interconnected through a Top-of-Rack (TOR) Ethernet switch which in turn connects to an aggregation switch, also known as End-of-Rack (EOR) switch. The aggregation switch connects to other aggregation switches and through these switches to other servers in the data center. A core switch connects to the various aggregation switches and provides connectivity to the outside world, typically through Layer 3 (IP). Since most of intra-data center traffic traverses only the TOR and the aggregation switches, a fat-tree topology is proposed to address this anomaly. The presence of virtualized servers adds an extra dimension. Network connections to physical servers will need to involve “bigger pipes” because traffic for multiple Virtual Machines (VMs) will be multiplexed onto the same physical Ethernet connection compared to the case in which the network connection is just used for standalone server. Data transfer and network bandwidth, WAN acceleration for the cloud, and VM migration are some of the perspectives on cloud computing networking, which we elaborate on them in more details in the sequel.

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for the cloud, and VM migration are some of the perspectives on cloud computing networking, which we elaborate on them in more details in the sequel. Some applications and protocols can benefit from WAN acceleration devices that can be used on both ends of a WAN link to cache and locally serve enterprise applications. These appliances are not specific to the cloud—they have been used for several years for application performance improvement when a WAN link is involved. Recently, virtual network appliances for WAN acceleration are also deployed.

1.2 Challenge in IaaS:

Some of the challenges in the existing cloud networks are:

- **APPLICATION PERFORMANCE:** Cloud tenants should be able to specify bandwidth requirements for applications hosted in the cloud, ensuring similar performance to on-premise deployments. Many tiered applications require some guaranteed bandwidth between server instances to satisfy user transactions within an acceptable time frame and meet predefined SLAs. Insufficient bandwidth between these servers will impose significant latency on user interactions. Therefore, without explicit control, variations in cloud workloads and oversubscription can cause delay and drift of response time beyond acceptable limits, leading to SLA violations for the hosted applications.
- **FLEXIBLE DEPLOYMENT OF APPLIANCES:** Enterprises deploy a wide variety of security appliances in their data centers, such as Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) or Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), and firewalls to protect their applications from attacks. These are often employed alongside other appliances that perform load balancing, caching and application acceleration. When deployed in the cloud, an enterprise application should continue to be able to flexibly exploit the functionality of these appliances.
- **POLICY ENFORCEMENT COMPLEXITIES:** Traffic isolation and access control to the end-users are among the multiple forwarding policies that should be enforced. These policies directly impact the configuration of each router and switch. Changing requirements, different protocols (e.g., OSPF, LAG, VRRP), different flavors of L2 spanning tree protocols, along with vendor specific protocols, make it

extremely challenging to build, operate and inter-connect a cloud network at scale.

- **TOPOLOGY DEPENDENT COMPLEXITY:** The network topology of data centers is usually tuned to match a pre-defined traffic requirement. For instance, a network topology, which is optimized for east-west traffic (i.e., traffic among servers in a data center), is not the same as the topology for north-south (traffic to/from the Internet). The topology designs also depends on how the L2 and/or L3 is utilizing the effective network capacity. For instance, adding a simple link and switch in the presence of a spanning tree based L2 forwarding protocol, may not provide additional capacity. Furthermore, evolving the topology based on traffic pattern changes also requires complex configuration of L2 and L3 forwarding rules.
- **APPLICATION REWRITING:** Applications should run “out of the box” as much as possible, in particular for IP addresses and for network-dependent failover mechanisms. Applications may need to be rewritten or reconfigured before deployment in the cloud to address several network related limitations. Two key issues are: 1) lack of a broadcast domain abstraction in the cloud network and 2) cloud-assigned IP addresses for virtual servers.
- **LOCATION DEPENDENCY:** Network appliances and servers (e.g., hypervisors) are typically tied to a statically configured physical network, which implicitly creates a location dependency constraint. For instance, the IP address of a server is typically determined based on the VLAN or subnet it belongs to. VLAN and subnets are based on physical switch port configuration. Therefore, a VM cannot be easily and smoothly migrated across the network. Constrained VM migration decreases the level of resource utilization and flexibility. Besides, physical mapping of VLAN or subnet space to the physical ports of a switch often lead to a fragmented IP address pool.

As the most important protocol of 4G communication technology, LTE Advanced has two different standards: TD-LTE and FDD-LTE. These two modes correspond to two different duplex modes: TDD and FDD. TDD is what we call time division duplex. It means that uplink and downlink are crossed in the same frequency band according to time allocation, which can make better use of spectrum resources and facilitate layout; in addition, FDD is called frequency division duplex, which means that uplink and downlink are carried out simultaneously in different frequency bands. The advantage of FDD mode lies in its stronger data transmission capability. In fact, 4G uses OFDM to modulate downlink, while SC-OFDM to modulate uplink is quite different from 3G.

1.2 SDN-BASED CLOUD COMPUTING NETWORKING

SDN [7] is an emerging network architecture where “network control functionality” is decoupled from “forwarding functionality” and is directly programmable [6], [7]. This migration of control, formerly tightly integrated in individual networking equipment, into accessible computing devices (logically centralized) enables the underlying infrastructure to be “abstracted” for applications and network services. Therefore, applications can treat the network as a logical or virtual entity. As a result, enterprises and carriers gain unprecedented programmability, automation, and network control, enabling them to build innovative, highly scalable, flexible networks that readily adapt to changing business needs.

A logical view of the SDN architecture is depicted in Figure 3. OpenFlow is the first standard interface designed specifically for SDN, providing high-performance, granular traffic control across multiple vendors’ network devices. Network intelligence is logically centralized in SDN control software (e.g. OpenFlow controllers), which maintain a global view of the network. As a result, the network, in its ultimate abstracted view, appears as a single logical switch. Adapting SDN architecture, greatly simplifies the design and operation of networks since it removes the need to know and understand the operation details of hundreds of protocols/standards. Enterprises and carriers gain vendor-independent control over the entire network from a single logical point.

Fig 2

In addition to the network abstraction, SDN architecture will provide and support a set of APIs that simplifies the implementation of common network services (e.g., slicing, virtualization, routing, multicast, security, access control, bandwidth management, traffic engineering, QoS, processor and/or storage optimization, energy consumption, and various forms of policy management). SDN's promise is to enable the following key features:

- Programmatic approach to dynamically create/deploy virtual networks
- Decoupled virtual network topology from the actual physical network topology
- Co-existence of multiple virtual networks based on a shared physical network
- Support isolation ensuring independent operation of virtual networks
- Enhanced resource utilization of physical networks through network resource pooling
- Reduced network design and (re) configuration time and complexities
- Instantiation of flexible virtual networks to meet diverse requirements

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

COMPARISION OF EXISTING VIRTUAL NETWORKING

IMPLEMENTATIONS:

Cloud networking infrastructure and server virtualization are more or less the same thing as far as the technology is concerned. Both services have to be scalable, on-demand and orchestrated. In an ideal situation the physical network will provide the transport, and the hypervisors will provide the VM service and the virtual networks will be constructed on top of the transport network. There is a whole range of solutions that can be utilized to implement the virtual networks (segments). The traditional approach is to implement the virtual segments using VLANs, which are limited to 4096 segments (VLANs) and therefore not really scalable.

There are some proposals, which suggest to utilize IEEE 802.1ad (Q-in-Q) to address 4K limitation, but there is no orchestration support for Q-in-Q currently. On the other extreme, Amazon EC2 is utilizing IP over IP with a rich control plane to provide virtual segments. VMware networking (Arista VM Tracer), Edge Virtual Bridging (IBM's EVB, IEEE 802.1Qbg), vCloud Director Networking Infrastructure (vCDNI) (VMware, MAC over MAC) or EVB with PBB/SPB, VXLAN (Cisco), Network Virtualization using Generic Routing Encapsulation (NVGRE) (Microsoft) MAC over IP, and Nicira Network Virtualization Platform (NVP) (MAC over IP with a control plane) are other approaches. All of these proposals can be categorized into three architectural groups: a) dumb virtual switch in the hypervisor plus normal physical switch (e.g., traditional VLAN model), b) dumb virtual switch with intelligent physical switch (e.g., VM-aware networking, EVB), and c) Intelligent virtual switch plus a typical (L2/L3) physical switch.

SDN BASED FEDERATION:

There are general advantages to be realized by enterprises that adopt OpenFlow enabled SDN as the connectivity foundation for private and/or hybrid cloud connectivity. A logically centralized SDN control plane will provide a comprehensive view (abstract view) of data center and cloud resources and access network availability. This will ensure cloud federation (cloud extensions) are directed to adequately resourced data centers, on links providing sufficient bandwidth and service levels. Using the SDN terminologies, a high-level description of key building blocks for an SDN-based cloud federation are:

- OpenFlow enabled cloud backbone edge nodes, which connect to the enterprise and cloud provider data center
- OpenFlow enabled core nodes which efficiently switch traffic between these edge nodes
- An OpenFlow and/or SDN-based controller to configure the flow forwarding tables in the cloud backbone nodes and providing a WAN network virtualization application (e.g. Optical Flow Visor).
- Hybrid cloud operation and orchestration software to manage the enterprise and provider data center federation, inter-cloud workflow, and resource management of compute/storage and inter-data center network management.

FIGURE 3

CONCLUSION

In this article the infrastructure as a service (IaaS) architecture and key challenges with a focus on virtual networks and cloud federation were presented. IaaS has provided a flexible model, in which customers are billed according to their compute usage, storage consumption, and the duration of usage. Some of the challenges in the existing Cloud Networks are: guaranteed performance of applications when applications are moved from on-premises to the cloud facility, flexible deployment of appliances (e.g., deep packet inspection, intrusion detection systems, or firewalls), and associated complexities to the policy enforcement and topology dependence. A typical three layer data center network includes TOR layer connecting the servers in a rack, aggregation layer and core layer, which provides connectivity to/from the Internet edge. This multi-layer architecture imposes significant complexities in defining boundaries of L2 domains, L3 forwarding networks and policies, and layer-specific multi-vendor networking equipment. Applications should run “out of the box” as much as possible, in particular for IP addresses and for network-dependent failover mechanisms. Network appliances and servers (e.g., hypervisors) are typically tied to a statically configured physical network, which implicitly creates a location dependency constraint. SDN architecture in addition to decoupling the data forwarding and control planes will provide and support a set of APIs that simplify the implementation of common network services. VLAN, VM-aware networking, vCDNI, VXLAN and Nicira NVP are technologies to provide virtual networks in cloud infrastructures. Nicira NVP, which utilizes MAC in IP encapsulation and external control plane provides the efficient solution for virtual network implementation. OpenFlow core and edge nodes with a proper OpenFlow controller can be considered as a novel cloud federation mechanism. SDN-based federation will facilitate multi-vendor networks between enterprise and service provider data centers, helping enterprise customers to choose best-in-class vendors Network fabric, which is a proposal for network edge version of OpenFlow is one of the recent proposals towards extension of SDN to increase the simplicity and flexibility of future network designs. What we should make clear, is that SDN does not, by itself, solve all the issues of cloud computing.

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